

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution, Transition Probability and Large Number of Particles

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In (1) it is suggested that a number of systems in nature have a total number of states with energy less than or equal to energy E proportional to E to the power of k (where k is of the order of the number particles). It is then shown that this leads to a power law distribution $(E-e_i)$ power $k-1$ where e_i is the energy of a single particle. In (2) it is shown that the power law distribution follows from a Fokker-Planck equation with appropriate friction and diffusion coefficients. It is also stated in (2) that reaction balance requires: $P(q) w(q, q_1) = P(q_1) w(q_1, q)$ where $P(q)$ is the probability to be in state q and $w(q, q_1)$ is the transition rate from q to q_1 .

If the power exponent of the power law distribution (which from (1) is proportional to the number of particles) becomes very large (i.e. approaches infinite), it becomes a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution (proportional to $\exp(-e_i/T)$). Then, $P(q)/P(q_1) = \exp(-(E(q)-E(q_1))/T) = w(q_1, q)/w(q, q_1)$ which is not the result which holds for a power law.

Traditionally, the MB distribution may be obtained (3) by considering the total number of arrangements (distributions) of a total energy E among N particles. This is written as $N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!$. It is then assumed that N is very large and Stirling's approximation applied to the \ln of the total number of arrangements. The underlying idea is that each arrangement carries the same weight. $\ln(\text{Number of arrangements})$ in the high N limit is then maximized with respect to $n(e_i)$ subject to the constraint: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i P(e_i)$ to obtain the MB distribution. Thus the MB distribution again appears because of a high N limit.

In this note, we examine the assumption that all energy arrangements carry the same weight. Reaction balance for two body scattering is: $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)P(e_4)$ with $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$. Thus there is no transition probability linked to say velocity. If there were, then different energy distribution arrangements would not necessarily carry the same weight. For example, $P(e_i)$ may be very low for a high e_i , but such a particle has a high velocity. If particle density is low, such a particle would move through a large region in space compared with a particle with low velocity. One might expect a factor linked to space covered to be multiplied by $P(e_i)$ when considering reaction balance, but this is not the case in the MB formulation. In the MB case, one considers only $P(e_i)$. This seems to suggest that each small region of space has a large number of particles so that the velocity of a particle does not really affect the probability to scatter. Thus assuming equal weights of variations distributions of energy (or arrangements) seems to automatically assume large numbers of particles. One then does not need to introduce the assumption of a high N a second time in order to justify using Stirling's approximation. In fact, it seems one does not need to use Stirling's approximation, because the derivative of $\ln(n(e_i)!+1)$ subject to the average energy constraint yields the MB distribution for $n(e_i) \gg 1$ which is already assumed by considering equal weights for all arrangements.

Power Law Distribution

In (1) it is suggested that many systems in nature follow the following law:

Number of states \leq energy E is proportional to E^k ((1))

Then the number of states between $E-\delta$ and $E+\delta$ is given as:

$$2 \delta E^{k-1} \quad ((2))$$

If one removes a particle with energy e_i , $E-e_i$ remains and the number of states is proportional to:

$$2 \delta (E-e_i)^{k-1} \quad ((3))$$

I.e. a power law. In (1) it is stated that k is proportional to the number of particles present, so for $N \rightarrow$ infinite one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution:

$$P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((4))$$

One may note that

$$P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j) \quad ((5))$$

For two body elastic scattering: $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4) \quad ((6))$

There are no extra factors linked to the interaction such as factors related to the velocity of the particle where $e_i=p_i^2/2m$ (one dimension nonrelativistic case).

From ((6)) one may obtain the MB distribution by taking \ln of the probability expression and equating to the conservation of energy equation multiplied by a constant i.e. $-1/T$.

For the power law, however, $P(e_1)P(e_2) \neq P(e_1+e_2) \quad ((7))$

In (2) the power law distribution is obtained as a solution of the Fokker-Planck equation with special values for the friction and diffusion coefficients. Reaction balance is defined as:

$$P(q)w(q,q_1) = P(q_1)w(q_1,q) \quad ((8))$$

One requires not only probabilities, but a separate transition function $w(q,q_1)$. Such is not the case in the MB situation. It seems there are two properties associated with the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution:

((A)) A large number of particles N is required.

((B)) Collision probabilities only depend on products of $P(e_i)$ as seen in ((6))

In this note, we ask: Are ((A)) and ((B)) independent assumptions?

Energy Arrangements, Factorials and the MB Distribution

Traditionally, the MB distribution is obtained by assuming equal weights for energy distributions (arrangements) of a total energy E among N particles. (3). In (3), the idea ((1)) is presented which leads to a power law distribution, but later a factorial approach is introduced which in the high N limit yields the MB distribution as it does for the power law. Thus there is consistency.

What is implied by stating that all energy distributions carry the same weight? It may be noted that this is a key assumption, otherwise one cannot use factorials to calculate the number of ways to distribute a total energy E among N particles. It seems it means that in the average situation:

$$\text{Product over } i P(e_i) = \text{constant where Sum over } i e_i = E \quad ((7))$$

This suggests $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ or equivalently $P(e_i) = C$ constant to the power of $-e_i/T$. This in turn seems to suggest there is no velocity dependent transition function in addition to $P(e_i)$ associated with two body collisions. The probability for e_1 and e_2 to collide is $P(e_1)P(e_2)$ etc. We ask: Does this make sense?

Consider the case for which $P(e_i)$ is very small for a high energy e_1 . $e_1 = p_1^2/2m$ so v_1 (velocity) is very high as well. This implies the particle moves a large distance in a small time compared with a particle with a low velocity. It would seem that the fast moving particle should have the chance to strike more particles based on its high velocity, especially in a low density system. Thus one might suggest:

$$P(e_i) \text{ function(velocity)} \quad ((8))$$

as the probability for a particle with e_i to collide, not simply $P(e_i)$. This would, however, render the idea of using factorials to count the number of state useless, because different states would contain different probabilities because of function(velocity). As a result, one must assume that:

$$\text{function(velocity)} = 1 \quad ((9))$$

This is equivalent to stating that there is no benefit of having a high velocity over a low one for collisions. This in turn means, we argue, that the number of particles in each little region of space be very high i.e.

$$N \text{ the number of particles is very large} \quad ((10))$$

Thus, we argue that the assumption of equal weights for each energy arrangement already implies a large number of particles. As a result, assumptions ((A)) and ((B)) are the same

If one has N particles, then the number of ways to distribute energy is:

$$\# \text{ arrangements} = N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \quad ((11))$$

Taking ln of ((11)) yields: $\ln(\text{arrangements}) = \ln(N!) - \sum_i \ln(n(e_i)!) \quad ((12))$

It is usually suggested that one may now make the assumption of large N, $n(e_i)$ and use Stirling's approximation:

$$\ln(n(e_i)!) \approx n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) \quad ((13))$$

We argue that the large N assumption must be used otherwise the factorial approach itself may be invalid because of non-equal weights for various arrangements.

Using ((3)) and a relaxed constraint: $\sum_i P(e_i) e_i = \text{Average} \quad ((14))$

one may maximize: $-\sum_i n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) + b \sum_i e_i n(e_i) \quad ((15))$

to obtain the MB distribution $C \exp(-e_i/T)$ where $b = 1/T$.

Given that a large N approximation is already included in the assumption of equal weights, we argue that one does not really need to use Stirling's approximation. One may instead define the derivative of $\ln(n(e_i)!) as:$

$$\text{Derivative with respect to } n \text{ of } \ln(n(e_i)!) = \ln([n(e_i)+1]) - \ln(n(e_i)!) = \ln(n(e_i)+1) \quad ((16))$$

In such a case one may maximize the factorial expression subject to $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = \text{Eave}$. $n(e_i)$ is already assumed to be a large number. One again obtains the MB distribution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that a power law with the exponent proportional to N, the number of particles, becomes a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in the high N limit. For two body scattering, the product of two MB distributions is the MB distribution of the sum of energies i.e. $\exp(-e_1/T) \exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-(e_1+e_2)/T)$. Thus for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, $PMB(e_1)PMB(e_2) = PMB(e_3)PMB(e_4)$. This result does not hold for the power law case. Furthermore, one might ask why the probability to collide only depends on the probabilities $PMB(e_1)$ and $PMB(e_2)$. One might think that functions of velocity should appear.

For example, a fast moving particle traverses a greater length than a slow one in the same time and this should enhance the probability to collide, especially in a low density scenario. In such a case, one would not have the MB distribution for collisions. Thus the MB result occurs not only for a large N scenario, but one for which collisions only depend on $PMB(e_i)$. Are these two independent conditions? We argue they may be the same. In order to drop a function of velocity, it must not matter that a particle with a high speed moves a greater distance (if there are no collisions) than a slow one. A way to ensure that a high speed is irrelevant for collisions is to have a high number of particles in each dx box about each x so that collisions happen immediately. Then there is no advantage to a high speed. What matters is the distribution $P(e_i)$

only. This we argue is important, because it means that if one distributes a total energy E among N particles, each arrangement has the same weight. The weight only depends on e_i and the product of $\exp(-e_i/T)$'s for a constant energy is the same. One may use factorials to calculate the number of arrangements. We stress, however, that in this scenario (equal weights) one has already assumed a high N . One may immediately use Stirling's approximation because high N is guaranteed. One does not need to introduce the idea of a high N as an independent assumption in addition to equal weights. Then maximizing $\ln(\# \text{ arrangements})$ with respect to the constraint $\sum_i e_i P(e_i)$ yields the MB distribution.

References

1. Plastino, A.R.; Plastino, A. Brief Review on the Connection between the Micro-Canonical Ensemble and the Sq-Canonical Probability Distribution. *Entropy* 2023, 25, 591.
[https://doi.org/ 10.3390/e25040591](https://doi.org/10.3390/e25040591)
https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/feeb/a0a0229fbe0835e6369c7def751d2553cd2b.pdf?_gl=1*1bd616d*_ga*MTA0MjMwNTQ0Ny4xNjY4Njg4MTc0*_ga_H7P4ZT52H5*MTY4MzU3NjkyNi44Ny4wLjE2ODM1NzY5MjkuMC4wLjA.
2. Ran, G. and Jiulin, D Are Power Law Distributions and Equilibrium Distribution or a Stationary Nonequilibrium Distribution <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1403.5441.pdf>
3. Reif, F. *Fundamentals of Statistical and Thermal Physics* (McGraw Hill, 1965)